

Anemia Risk Factor Model in Pregnant Women

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to analyze the risk factors and variables that most influence the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at Tilango Health Center after controlling for maternal risk factors such as gestational age, gestational spacing, knowledge, nutritional status, Antenatal Care, socioeconomic status, and parity. The sample in this study consisted of 120 pregnant women respondents in the Tilango Health Center area. The research design used was analytic with a cross-sectional approach. The results of the study were that there were factors that affected anemia in pregnant women, after controlling for risk factors for maternal gestational age P-value = 0.001 = $\alpha < 0.05$, pregnancy interval P-value = 0.038 = $\alpha < 0.05$, knowledge P-value = 0.042 = $\alpha < 0.05$, nutritional status P-value = 0.002 = $\alpha < 0.05$, ANC P-value = 0.019 = $\alpha < 0.05$, social status P-value = 0.001 = $\alpha < 0.05$ and parity P-value = 0.013 = $\alpha < 0.05$, the results of the multivariate variable that influences the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at gestational age with OR = 3.570. Therefore it is suggested to health workers to improve services to pregnant women in the form of health education related to the dangers of anemia in pregnant women and the importance of prenatal checks during pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Anemia, ANC, gestational age, pregnancy spacing, knowledge, nutritional status, social status and parity

INTRODUCTION

Maternal health is one of the priorities in developing Indonesia's human resources. Efforts to improve maternal health status are a form of investment in the future. According to Riskesdes data (2018), anemic pregnant women have a risk of death of up to 3.6 times greater than pregnant women who are not anemic. The results of Fidyah's research in Heliyana (2018) show that KEK affects anemia in pregnant women at the Tanjung Pinang City Health Center. The results of Zuhaida's research (2017) in Medan show a relationship between CED and anemia in pregnant women; pregnant women with CED have a four times higher risk of developing anemia compared to pregnant women who do not experience CED.

METHODS

Location and Research time

The research was conducted for two months in 2023; the location was the Tilango Health Center, Gorontalo Regency.

Population and sample

The population is pregnant women in the Tilango Health Center working area of as many as xxxx people. The sample is pregnant women, and as many as XX people were obtained by purposive random sampling.

INSTRUMENTS AND MATERIALS

The research instrument uses a questionnaire taken from the results of previous studies.

DATA ANALYSIS

The research data were analyzed using the Chi-Square test to find the relationship between research variables, then logistic regression analysis to find the most related variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of the effect of gestational age on pregnant women with the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

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Bivariate analysis

Table 1. Analysis of the Influence of Pregnancy Age on the Incidence of Anemia at the Tilango Health Center

Age Pregnancy	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		No Anemia			%	
	n		n				
At risk	51	42,5	25	20,8	76	63,3	0.001
No At risk	16	13,3	28	23,3	44	36,7	
Total	67	55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.001 (<0.05), meaning there is a significant effect between gestational age and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center.

The results of the analysis of the effect of pregnancy spacing on pregnant women with the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table

Table 2. Analysis of the Influence of Distance between Pregnancy and Anemia Incidence at the Tilango Health Center

Distance Pregnancy	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		No Anemia			%	
< 2 years		35,8	24	20	67	55,8	0.038
≥ 2 Years		20	29	24,2	53	44,2	
Total		55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.038 (<0.05), meaning that there is a significant and significant effect between pregnancy spacing and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center . The results of the analysis of the influence of knowledge of pregnant women on the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 3. Analysis of the Effect of Knowledge of Pregnant Women on the Incidence of Anemia at the Tilango Health Center

Knowledge	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		No Anemia			%	
Not enough		36,7	25	20,8	69	57,5	0.042
Enough		19,2	28	23,3	51	42,5	
Total		55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.042 (<0.05), meaning there is a significant and significant influence between knowledge and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center . The results of the analysis of the influence of the nutritional status of pregnant women on the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 4. Analysis of the Effect of Nutritional Status of Pregnant Women on the Incidence of Anemia at the Tilango Health Center

Nutritional Status	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		Anemia			%	
Less KEK		35,8	19	15,8	62	51,7	0.002
KEK Normal		20	34	28,3	58	48,3	
Total		55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.002 (<0.05), meaning there is a significant influence between nutritional status and

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the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center. The results of the analysis of the relationship between Antenatal Care (ANC) and the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 5. Analysis of the Effect of Antenatal Care (ANC) on the Incidence of Anemia at the Tilango Health Center

ANC	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		No Anemia				
Complete		16,7	27	22,5	47	39,2	0.019
No Complete		39,2	26	21,7	73	60,8	
Total		55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.019 (<0.05), meaning there is a significant and significant influence between ANC status and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center . The results of the analysis of the effect of social status on the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 6. Analysis of the Influence of Social Status on the Incidence of Anemia at the Tilango Health Center

Social Status	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		Anemia				
>UMP		22,5	37	30,8	64	53,3	0.001
MP		33,3	16	13,4	56	46,7	
tal		55,8		44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.001 (<0.05), meaning that there is a significant and significant influence between social status and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center . The results of the analysis of the effect of parity on the incidence of anemia at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 7. Analysis of the Relationship between Gender and the Incidence of COVID-19

Parity	Incident Anemia				Total		P-values
	Anemia		Anemia				
Primipara		20	31	25,8	55	45,8	0.013
Multipara		38,5	22	18,3	65	54,2	
tal		55,8	53	44,2	120	100	

Source : Primary Data, 2023

The Chi-Square Test value obtained P-value = 0.013 (<0.05), meaning there is a significant and significant influence between parity status and the incidence of anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center .

Multivariate Analysis

The results of the multivariate analysis of risk factors for anemia in pregnant women at the Tilango Health Center are presented in the following table:

Table 8. Analysis of Factors Influencing the Event of COVID-19

No	Variable Study	Sig	Odds Ratio
1	Age Pregnancy	0.001	3,570
2	Distance Pregnancy	0.040	2.165
3	Knowledge	0.043	2,143
4	Nutritional Status	0.002	3,206
5	ANC	0.020	0.410
6	Parity	0.014	2,525
7	Social Status	0.002	0.292

Source : Primary Data, 2023

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Table 8 shows the results of the Multivariate Test; it was found that of the seven variables that had been tested, it was found that all variables had a P-value = <0.05. This means that all variables significantly affect the incidence of anemia in pregnant women. The OR value of gestational age was 3,570, which means that respondents who were at risk of gestational age (trimester I and II) had a risk of 3,570 times experiencing anemia. The OR value of pregnancy spacing was 2.165, meaning respondents with a pregnancy interval of <2 years had 2.165 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of knowledge is 2.143, meaning respondents with less knowledge have 2.143 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of nutritional status is 3.206, meaning that respondents with less CED have 2.143 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of ANC status is 0.410, meaning that respondents with incomplete ANC status have 0.410 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of parity status is 2.525, which means that respondents who have primipara parity status have a risk of experiencing anemia 2.525 times. The OR value of social status was 0.292, meaning respondents with social status <UMP had a risk of experiencing anemia 0.292 times.

Based on the research results of the multivariate test results, it was found that of the seven variables that had been tested, it was found that all variables had a P-value = <0.05. This means that all variables have a significant relationship with the incidence of anemia in pregnant women. The OR value of gestational age was 3,570, which means that respondents who were at risk of gestational age (trimester I and II) had a risk of experiencing anemia 3,570 times. The OR value of pregnancy spacing was 2.165, meaning respondents with <2 years of pregnancy spacing had 2.165 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of knowledge is 2.143, meaning respondents with less knowledge have 2.143 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of nutritional status is 3.206, meaning that respondents with less CED have 2.143 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of ANC status is 0.410, meaning that respondents with incomplete ANC status have 0.410 times the risk of experiencing anemia. The OR value of parity status is 2.525, which means that respondents who have primipara parity status have a risk of experiencing anemia 2.525 times. The OR value of social status was 0.292, meaning respondents with social status <UMP had a risk of experiencing anemia 0.292 times. Based on the OR table above, gestational age significantly influences the incidence of anemia.

According to Wiknjastro's theory (2010), Hemodilution or blood dilution during pregnancy will reach a maximum of 5-8 months; this hemodilution factor can cause the mother's blood hemoglobin level to decrease to 10 gr/dl. The increasing age of the mother's pregnancy, the greater the risk of suffering from anemia if it is not balanced with a balanced diet and regular consumption of Fe. This is caused by physiological changes in pregnancy that begin in the 6th week of pregnancy, namely the increase in plasma volume, which reaches its peak at the 26th week, resulting in a decrease in Hb levels (37).

This aligns with research conducted by Harna et al. (2020), which found that pregnant women who experience the most anemia are pregnant women in the third trimester with a P-value = 0.000. The higher the gestational age, the lower the hemoglobin level in the mother's body. This is related to the physiological changes that occur during pregnancy. The increased need for blood volume and plasma results in decreased hematocrit and blood plasma protein levels, usually occurring from the sixth week of gestation to the third trimester. Therefore, gestational age is a factor that significantly influences the incidence of anemia in pregnant women (38).

CONCLUSIONS

The variable that has the most influence on the incidence of anemia in pregnant women is the variable gestational age with OR = 3.570.

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